

Schmidt Ocean Institute Post Expedition Report

Microbes in Oxygen Minimum Zones

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1 Overview

SOI Expedition ID	Fkt240412
Vessel	R/V <i>Falkor (too)</i>
Expedition Name	Microbes in Oxygen Minimum Zones
Expedition Dates	2024/04/12 - 2024/05/15
Departure Port	Antofagasta, Chile
Termination Port	Antofagasta, Chile
Ocean	South Pacific Ocean

Map of Expedition Location

Figure 1: Map of Expedition Location.

1.1 Expedition Overview

Oxygen minimum zones (OMZs) are regions of the ocean where dissolved oxygen is extremely low or undetectable. They occur naturally in parts of the water column where oxygen supply is limited and microbial respiration consumes oxygen faster than it can be replaced. The Eastern Tropical South Pacific (ETSP), off northern Chile, contains one of the world’s major oxygen minimum zones and is an important natural laboratory for understanding how marine ecosystems function under oxygen depletion.

Although OMZs are inhospitable to most animals, they support diverse microbial communities that drive major transformations of carbon, nitrogen, and greenhouse gases. The inhabiting microorganisms influence whether nitrogen is retained in forms that sustain marine productivity or lost from the ocean, and they may contribute to the production or consumption of nitrous oxide, a powerful greenhouse gas. Understanding these microbial processes is increasingly important because low-oxygen regions are expected to expand as the ocean warms.

This expedition focused on linking microbial identity, activity, and ecosystem function across sharp oxygen gradients in the Eastern Tropical South Pacific. It combined high-resolution water-column measurements, shipboard experiments, *in situ* incubations, sampling for molecular signatures of bacteria, archaea and viruses, phytoplankton ecophysiology, and trace-oxygen sensing to examine how microbial communities operate from oxygenated surface waters through the oxycline and into anoxic waters.

A central motivation for the expedition was that traditional sampling can alter low-oxygen seawater before it is studied. Oxygen can enter samples during collection and handling, and this contamination can change microbial activity and bias measurements of processes that are highly sensitive to oxygen. To reduce these artifacts, the science team used and tested specialized instruments designed to sample, incubate, and monitor seawater under conditions closer to those found in the ocean.

1.2 Authorizations and Permitting

Permit Number	Permit Authority	Permit Focus
JEMGA ORD 13270-916	SHOA (Chilean Navy)	Research

1.3 Expedition Timeline

The expedition began on April 12, 2024, departing from Antofagasta, Chile, and returned to Antofagasta, Chile on May 15, 2024.

1.4 Expedition Objectives

The primary objective of the expedition was to determine how microorganisms control carbon and nitrogen cycling across oxygen gradients in the ETSP OMZ. The expedition targeted key processes including nitrification, denitrification, anammox, aerobic respiration, and inorganic

carbon fixation. These measurements were designed to improve understanding of how oxygen loss affects nutrient availability, greenhouse gas dynamics, and microbial community structure.

A second objective was to compare *in situ* measurements with conventional shipboard incubations. We deployed *in situ* incubation systems that minimized oxygen contamination and continuously monitored oxygen conditions, while also conducting parallel laboratory incubations using water collected with standard methods. This comparison was intended to identify how traditional sampling may alter measured rates of microbial processes in oxygen-depleted waters.

The expedition also aimed to identify the microorganisms responsible for key biogeochemical processes. This included collecting samples for metagenomics, metatranscriptomics, single-cell genomics, viral analyses, ammonia-oxidizing archaea activity measurements, and microbial cell abundance. By pairing biological measurements with detailed chemical and oxygen profiles, the project sought to connect microbial community composition and gene expression with measured ecosystem functions.

A final objective was to examine how low oxygen affects photosynthetic microorganisms and virus-microbe interactions. We investigated why many phytoplankton groups decline near the oxycline, how some cyanobacteria may persist in low-oxygen waters, and how viruses may influence microbial populations and nutrient cycling within the oxygen minimum zone. Together, these objectives support more accurate predictions of how expanding low-oxygen regions may affect marine ecosystems, biogeochemical cycles, and climate-relevant processes.

2 Expedition Accomplishments

The expedition was organized around the project's main scientific objectives, with each team contributing a focused area of expertise while coordinating sampling across shared stations and oxygen gradients.

1) **In situ team** (Laura Bristow, Sina Schorn, Alisa Wuest, Morten Larsen, Chris Basque) worked on measuring nitrogen cycling and related microbial processes under conditions as close as possible to those in the ocean, using *in situ* incubation approaches and trace-oxygen measurements. This team also conducted onboard comparisons of the same processes.

2) **Microbiaki Lab** (Maria Pachiadaki, Liza Osorio Pando, Taylor Muric) focused on linking microbial community composition and gene expression to oxygen gradients and biogeochemical processes through metagenomic and metatranscriptomic sampling to unveil the microbial responses to various oxygen regimes.

3) **AOA team** (Beate Kraft, Elisa Hernandez Magaña) focused on the abundance, diversity, and activity of ammonia-oxidizing archaea in oxygen-depleted waters, including their potential role in nitrogen cycling under anoxia.

4) **Viral team** (Julia Brown, Tim D'Angelo, Annabelle Adams-Beyea) surveyed the viral abundance, diversity, activity, virus-host interactions, and the potential role of viruses in OMZ microbial ecology and nutrient cycling.

5) **Phytoplankton team** (Osvaldo Ulloa, Peter von Dassow, Montserrat Aldunate, Fabián Cortés, Emilio Espinoza, Gadiel Alarcón, Gerardo García) worked on phytoplankton physiology, Prochlorococcus ecology, nutrient gradients, and carbon fixation across the oxycline and anoxic waters of the ETSP.

6) **MEB Lab** (Emilio García-Robledo, Julia Huggins, Elisa Angulo-Cánovas) focused on oxygen consumption, aerobic respiration, transitions between aerobic and anaerobic metabolism, and high-resolution trace-oxygen measurements in OMZ waters.

7) **HyperPro team** (Bror Jönsson) characterized the underwater light field to provide optical context for phytoplankton physiology and carbon fixation measurements.

2.1 At-sea Accomplishments

2.1.1 Science

1) In-Situ team

Main aim: Determine rates and elucidate pathways and players in the web of microbial processes that drive nitrogen recycling and loss in the ETSP oxygen minimum zone.

The nitrogen transformation experiments focused on two specific areas:

i) Recycling vs. loss: Nitrite plays a pivotal role in the nitrogen cycle serving as a substrate for N_2 -producing denitrification and anammox as well as for nitrite oxidation, recycling nitrogen to nitrate. Determination of the extent of recycling versus loss in OMZ systems has to date been limited by the inherent oxygen contamination within our lab incubations; oxygen easily diffuses through the plastic and rubber components of experimental setups; hence, these experiments are likely not carried out under the in situ oxygen concentrations of the OMZ core, and therefore may over or under estimate process rates.

To address these issues and evaluate potential biases incurred by the sampling and handling of OMZ waters, a newly modified version of the IPS was deployed, CockTail (Chamber Oxygen Collector Kit Trace Analyzer In situ Logger; see technical details in the section below), in which all plastics, and hence sources of oxygen contamination have been replaced with glass and titanium. Thereby, allowing us to carry out incubations with ^{15}N stable isotopes in situ while oxygen levels were monitored throughout the incubation in and outside the incubation chamber. Two incubators were deployed side by side, initially deployed on a drifting mooring, and then to enable quick turnaround times between incubations was deployed directly off the A-frame. Two experiment combinations were conducted across the four chambers of the two instruments (triple chamber and single chamber instruments):

A) two chambers receiving $^{15}NO_2^-$ allowing us to capture anammox, denitrification and nitrite oxidation rates, the third chamber receiving $^{15}NO_2^-$ + approx. 500nM O_2 to look at oxygen response and the fourth chamber $^{15}NO_3^-$ for the determination of nitrate reduction (first step of denitrification).

B) all chambers received $^{15}\text{NO}_2^-$, but with varying oxygen conditions across the four chambers (no O_2 addition, 500 nM, 1000 nM and 2000 nM), allowing us to assess the oxygen response across a broader range of oxygen concentrations than in scenario A.

In both A) and B) scenarios all chambers that received $^{15}\text{NO}_2^-$ also received $^{13}\text{C-HCO}_3^-$, to assess single cell rates of dark carbon fixation.

Ten in situ deployments were carried out in total, spanning oxygen gradients of below detection to approx. 2 μM and 85 to 300 m water depth. With seven of these deployments following the experiment combination of scenario A and the others scenario B. For each deployment, parallel lab incubations were carried out at the same depth (sampled from Niskin bottles) to measure process rates following standard procedures to identify potential biases incurred by conventional sampling.

While in situ incubations are an essential step forward allowing us to quantify and isolate potential effects of sampling, it can not replace an extensive laboratory-based experimental program, due to the number of depths and tracer combinations required to look at the full suite of nitrogen cycling processes in these systems. Hence high resolution depth profiles (15 depths) were carried out at both stations using standard procedures to elucidate rates of anammox, denitrification, nitrate reduction, and nitrite oxidation. In addition, at a subset of these depths, kinetics experiments were performed looking at the influence of varying O_2 and NO_2^- concentrations on anammox, denitrification and nitrite oxidation rates, and also directly aligned experiments with $^{13}\text{C-HCO}_3^-$ added, were undertaken to assess single cell rates of dark carbon fixation.

ii) N_2O production and consumption: Notable hotbeds of N_2O (a highly potent greenhouse gas) accumulation and emission in the oceans include coastal upwelling systems such as the ETSP. Recent experimental evidence suggests that N_2O production in OMZ waters may occur through non-canonical pathways. We conducted a series of laboratory-based experiments using ^{15}N and ^{18}O -labeled substrates in unique combinations to look at the full suite of potential N_2O producing and consuming pathways. Experiments were conducted across high resolution depths profiles (8 depths) and at various concentrations of added oxygen and N_2O to look at the kinetic response. Experiments were complemented by high resolution profiles of N_2O concentrations sampled from the PPS).

Additionally, the *mTail* (*mini Trace analyzer in situ logger*), a state of the art three channel oxygen logger specially designed for high resolution ultra-sensitive oxygen sensors, was utilized for the first time during this cruise (see technical details in the section below). The unit was deployed in three different configurations to obtain a novel overarching dataset of oxygen dynamics:

- 1) CTD rosette: mounted on the CTD rosette, over 70 high resolution oxygen profiles were collected. This included the two tow-yo sections between our two sampling stations. In addition, testing was undertaken to look at the extent of oxygen contamination from collecting and sampling OMZ waters in Niskin bottles.
- 2) Pump Profiling System (PPS): mounted on the PPS unit, 2 high resolution oxygen profiles were collected.

- 3) Mini-Drifter: in a unique application, mTail was connected to a surface drifter and deployed at target depths of 180, 120, 100 and 80 m to look at oxygen dynamics within the OMZ oxycline and core; deployments lasted between 6 and 24 hours, with 11 conducted in total.

2) Microbiaki Lab

Main aim: Determine rates and elucidate pathways and players in the web of microbial processes that drive nitrogen cycling and loss in the ETSP oxygen minimum zone.

The Microbiaki Lab work involved three different approaches:

i) Microbial community diversity and functional potential: Around 6 L of whole and size-fractionated water were collected for community DNA analysis (metagenomics). Size fractionation was performed by serially passing samples through a 1.6 μm filter and then a 0.22 μm filter in stacked Swinnex filter holders. Samples were collected both from Niskin bottles using a peristaltic pump in the ship's laboratory and in situ using the Microbial Sampler (MS). All filters, either membrane filters or Sterivex filters, were stored at -80°C .

ii) Metatranscriptomics: Whole-water and size-fractionated samples were collected for community RNA analysis. Size fractionation was performed by serially passing samples through a 2.7 μm filter and then a 0.22 μm filter in stacked filter holders. Samples were collected from Niskin bottles using a peristaltic pump in the ship's laboratory and in situ using the Microbial Sampler. All filters, either membrane filters or Sterivex filters, were preserved in RNAlater and stored at -80°C . These samples will be used to examine microbial gene expression across oxygenated, low-oxygen, and anoxic waters and to link transcriptomic activity with measured biogeochemical rates.

A central goal of this approach was to acquire expression profiles with minimal bias through in situ filtration and preservation. In oxygen-depleted waters, microbial activity and gene expression can change rapidly when samples are brought to the surface, exposed to changing pressure and temperature, or contaminated with oxygen during recovery and handling. RNA is especially sensitive because it has a short half-life, and previous studies have shown that gene-expression profiles can be affected by the sampling method. The MS was therefore used to collect and preserve samples at depth, closer to their natural oxygen, pressure, and temperature conditions. This approach is expected to provide a more accurate view of the active microbial community and to strengthen comparisons between transcript abundance and measured rates of nitrogen, sulfur, and carbon cycling. Shipboard filters were gathered as back-up.

iii) Single-cell genomics of Bacteria and Archaea: Small volumes of whole water (1 mL) were aliquoted under a helium atmosphere using a glove box. GlyTE (100 μL) was added to two of the aliquots, which were then frozen at -80°C . Redox-Sensor Green (1 μL) was added to the other two aliquots, which were incubated in the dark at in situ temperatures for 30 minutes. At the end of the incubation, GlyTE (100 μL) was added, and the samples were subsequently frozen at -80°C . These samples will be used to examine single-cell genomic diversity and the redox activity of bacterial and archaeal cells across oxygen regimes.

In summary, the Microbiaki Lab collected paired metagenomic, metatranscriptomic, and single-cell samples to connect microbial identity, genomic potential, gene expression, and single-cell activity with oxygen gradients and rate measurements of key nitrogen, sulfur, and carbon cycling processes. The inclusion of in situ filtration and preservation was designed to reduce sampling artifacts and improve the reliability of molecular signatures from oxygen-depleted waters.

3) AOA team

Main aim: Map the abundance of AOA along the oxycline and into the core of the OMZ; assess the diversity and activity of ammonia-oxidizing archaea in oxygen depleted waters below the oxycline on the population as well as single cell level.

The AOA experiments focused on four specific areas:

i) High resolution abundance profile of ammonia-oxidizing Archaea: To obtain high resolution cell abundance profiles from 0m to 250 m depths, samples were collected with the PPS together with the Phytoplankton team (1 high resolution profiles for station 1 and 2 for station 2). The profiles obtained by the pump profiling system supplemented with high resolution CTD casts 1 (station 1) or 2 (station2).

50ml of sample was fixed with 2% formaldehyde overnight at 4°C, subsequently washed with phosphate buffered saline (PBS) and filtered onto 0.2. μm polycarbonate filters. Filters were dried and frozen. AOA cells will be identified and quantified with catalyzed reporter deposition fluorescence in situ hybridization (CARD-FISH) using horseradish peroxidase labeled oligonucleotide probes followed by fluorescently labeled tyramide signal amplification. Filters will be counter-stained with DAPI and counted with an epifluorescence microscope.

ii) Single cell activity via click-chemistry based incubations: The activity of AOA under oxygen depletion on the single cell level was targeted in click chemistry-based incubation assays tracking de novo protein, DNA and RNA synthesis in incubations amended with the modified deoxynucleoside (thymidine analogue 5-ethynyl-2'-deoxyuridine), nucleoside (uridine analogue 5-ethynyl-uridine), or amino acids (l-azidohomoalanine and l-homopropargylglycine). Incubations were performed for 6 different depths at both stations. samples were collected from the CTD and transferred to serum bottles that were purged with helium. Then the different click chemistry substrates were added. After 24h of incubation samples were filtered onto polycarbonate filters, fixed with formaldehyde and frozen. Back at the University of Southern Denmark we will perform the click reaction, that fluorescently stains cells which incorporated the substrates. To identify cells the assay will be combined with CARD-FISH. That way we will be able to determine the fraction of AOA cells that were active at the different water depth sampled. This approach can also be extended to other microbial populations.

iii) Incubations for stable isotope probing proteomics: To determine newly synthesized proteins of active members of the microbial community particularly ammonia-oxidizing archaea and detect protein translation patterns specific to AOA exposed to oxygen depletion we performed incubations for stable isotope probing (SIP)-metaproteomics. Water was collected with the pump profiling system except for two incubations in which the water was collected with the CTD. Incubations were performed in three depths per station, amended with labelled ^{13}C -bicarbonate

and incubated for 18 h and 36 h. At least four replicates were collected per time point. Incubation volumes were 5 L. Incubations were performed under oxygen depletion after degassing incubation bottles with helium. For selected depths, incubations were also performed after oxygen was added back. Samples were collected on sterivex filters under constant helium flow and immediately flash frozen. Proteins will be extracted and proteomics analysis will be performed using a LC-MS/MS platform (orbitrap) which is needed to generate high mass resolution data for ¹³C-labeled peptides. Subsequent data analysis will be performed using the Calis-P analysis software. Our analysis will focus on newly synthesized proteins in AOA. However, we will also get insights into the proteome of other microbial community members. To our knowledge, this is the first time that such a SIP-proteomics approach has been performed for waters of an OMZ.

iv) Enrichment of ammonia-oxidizing Archaea: From the depths at which the click-chemistry incubations were performed water was also sampled for enrichments of AOA (3 depths per station). Water was transferred to serum bottles and amended with ammonium and oxygen concentrations were adjusted. Back at SDU enrichments will be monitored for nitrite accumulation and transferred accordingly.

In summary, the data generated here will provide unprecedented insights into the role of AOA in oxygen depleted water of the ETSP. Furthermore, together with data collected by PI Pachiadaki, that will inform about the genetic inventory of the AOA populations present in the ETSP, we will gain valuable understanding of the adaptations that let these AOA thrive under oxygen depletion.

4) Viral team

Main aim: Expand our understanding of the role of viruses within OMZs and discovery of new RNA viruses from this previously unexplored environment.

The virus sampling involved the following collections:

i) Viral diversity: Samples for viral omics were collected from CTD water at discrete depths, 9 to 10 times per station. Depths were targeted based on their location within the OMZ and based on sample selection by collaborating scientists Pachiadaki and Bristow. Samples were size-fractionated, and the filtrate containing virus-only water was concentrated. Each major sample included particle-associated and microbial planktonic DNA and RNA fractions, large-volume filtration material, virus concentrates, filters for viral RNA and DNA, flow cytometry samples, and single-cell genomics samples.

ii) Viral abundance: Samples were collected and preserved for flow cytometry counts of viruses and bacteria. In total, the team collected and preserved 172 samples for bacterial and viral flow cytometry counts. These samples will be used to examine viral and prokaryotic abundances across oxygen gradients and to determine how virus-to-bacteria ratios change within the OMZ.

In total, the Viral team collected 19 major samples during the cruise, amounting to more than 2,200 L of filtered seawater. From these major samples, they collected 114 filters for DNA from microbial planktonic and particle-sized samples, 114 filters for RNA from microbial planktonic

and particle-sized samples, 172 samples for bacterial and viral flow cytometry counts, 60 samples for single-cell genomics, 76 filters for viral RNA and DNA, and 19 virus concentrates. These collections will support viral metagenomics, RNA virus discovery, virus-host interaction analyses, and studies of the role of viruses in OMZ microbial ecology and biogeochemistry

5) Phytoplankton team

Main aim: Understand the effect of low oxygen on phytoplankton and to decipher the success of OMZ *Prochlorococcus*

The phytoplankton team conducted the following experiments:

i) Nutrient analysis: Samples were collected following the vertical gradient from the oxygenated surface to below the oxycline, focusing principally on the oxycline and the top of the anoxic layer. For the most part, this was done using the Pump Profiling System (PPS), which allows the collection of CTD, oxygen, and fluorescence profiles while continuously pumping water to the ship deck, allowing high precision in the vertical dimension and minimizing oxygen contamination. In some cases, samples were also collected from Niskin bottles on the CTD-rosette, both to compare results from the two sampling methods and when the PPS was unavailable.

The PPS was used for high-resolution profiles of nutrients, including nitrate, nitrite, phosphate, and silicic acid, by connecting it to a QuAAtro39 autoanalyzer and pumping water from the surface to 250 m. Continuous measurements pumping directly to the autoanalyzer were compared with discrete samples taken by hand from the PPS outflow and discrete samples from the Niskin bottles on the CTD-rosette.

ii) Optical analysis of microbes: Live analysis of the smallest pigmented microbial plankton, including picoplankton (<3 μm) and nanoplankton (3–20 μm), was performed onboard with an InFlux Mariner Flow Cytometer/Cell Sorter. Larger cells were observed using an Olympus inverted microscope and a Zeiss Axioscope epifluorescence microscope. Cell sorting followed by microscopy, as well as sequential filtration, allowed verification of cytometric identifications of pigmented microbes into the following classes: *Prochlorococcus*-like cells, phycoerythrin-containing picocyanobacteria, picoeukaryotic phytoplankton, nanoeukaryotic phytoplankton without phycoerythrin, and nanoeukaryotic phytoplankton with phycoerythrin.

iii) Collection of size-fractionated samples for nucleic acid analysis: Discrete samples for RNA and DNA were collected using the PPS from the upper oxygenated mixed layer, the top of the oxycline, the base of the oxycline or transparency maximum, and the top of the anoxic layer. For RNA, the filtration line was connected directly to the PPS and included 3 μm polycarbonate filters and 0.2 μm Sterivex filters. For DNA, 5 L were filtered through 3 μm polycarbonate filters and then onto 0.2 μm Sterivex filters using a peristaltic pump in the laboratory. On one occasion, a special effort was made to collect sufficient volume (100 L for the 3 μm fraction) to allow the generation of a metatranscriptome from both nano- and picoeukaryotes from the transparency maximum at the base of the oxycline, where plankton biomass was very low.

iv) Photosynthesis-irradiance curves and carbon-fixation rates: Photosynthesis-irradiance curves were performed along the oxygen gradient at six depths in Station 1 (5–69 m) and five depths in Station 2 (5–101 m) to evaluate the effect of oxygen concentrations on photosynthetic parameters in the phytoplankton community larger than 0.7 μm . PI curves were performed using 12 custom-made 1 L glass incubation bottles designed to avoid oxygen contamination and labeled with ^{13}C -bicarbonate.

To evaluate where in the oxycline chemosynthesis versus photosynthesis becomes more important, carbon fixation rates were measured along the oxygen gradient using light and dark bottle incubations. These experiments evaluated the picoplanktonic community between 0.3 and 3.0 μm . PPS samples were used to minimize oxygen contamination, with incubations performed at four depths at Station 1 and six depths at Station 2. Additional carbon fixation rates were measured at Station 2 using water from Niskin bottles collected at 72, 120, and 180 m.

v) Experimental responses of cultured phytoplankton to oxycline waters: To understand why the phytoplankton community of the mixed layer disappears in the oxycline despite high nutrient levels and often sufficient light levels, experiments were conducted comparing the responses of two phytoplankton species to water from the base of the mixed layer and from the transparency maximum. The cosmopolitan coccolithophore *Gephyrocapsa huxleyi* and the coastal diatom *Thalassiosira* sp. were selected as model organisms. Two types of experiments were performed: 72-hour incubations in 1 L experimental vessels, measuring changes in cell abundance, fluorescence, and variable fluorescence; and acute-response incubations of approximately 40 minutes using custom-made 5 mL mini-chambers.

vi) Testing the possible role of nitric oxide and bioluminescent bacteria: Mini-chamber experiments were used to test whether oxycline waters induce intracellular nitric oxide in phytoplankton. Cultured phytoplankton were pre-stained with DAF-FM Diacetate, a fluorescent sensor of intracellular nitric oxide, and exposed to seawater from the transparency maximum at the base of the oxycline or from the chlorophyll maximum at the base of the mixed layer. In parallel, the team tested for the presence of bioluminescent bacteria in oxycline and anoxic waters by capturing particle-associated bacteria onto 3 μm filters and free-living bacteria onto 0.2 μm filters, using those filters to inoculate agar plates made with seawater complete medium. Samples were taken from the fully oxygenated mixed layer, the base of the oxycline, and the anoxic core.

6) MEB Lab

Main aim: Characterize the aerobic respiration and the transition to anaerobic metabolic pathways as well as the microbial interaction of the microbial community.

The MEB Lab work focused on three main areas:

i) Kinetics of aerobic respiration and other oxygen-consuming processes: The team characterized the dependence of oxygen consumption by processes such as aerobic respiration, ammonium oxidation, and nitrite oxidation in communities exposed to a gradient of oxygen concentrations, from the bottom of the oxycline to the central part of the anoxic core of the OMZ. Oxygen consumption rates were measured in samples collected at different depths and incubated in full glass bottles. The oxygen concentration of the samples was adjusted to different oxygen levels,

and incubations were performed in the cold room for 18–22 hours. Changes in oxygen concentration through time were measured using LUMOS sensors for trace oxygen levels from 1 to 1500 nM and PyroScience trace oxygen sensors for samples with concentrations above 1500 nM. Oxygen consumption rates were measured as the rate of oxygen consumption over time.

ii) Relative relevance of aerobic and anaerobic processes along the oxygen gradient: As oxygen concentration decreases, different aerobic and anaerobic processes can coexist, and ambient oxygen concentration may determine the oxygen range in which these contrasting metabolisms overlap. To compare their relative rates and better define the transition from aerobic to anaerobic pathways, samples collected for oxygen consumption rates were also spiked with different combinations of ^{15}N isotopes. $^{15}\text{N-NO}_3^-$, $^{15}\text{N-NO}_2^-$, and $^{15}\text{N-NH}_4^+$ were added during consecutive days to measure multiple oxidation and reduction pathways, including ammonium and nitrite oxidation, denitrification, DNRA, and anammox. Samples for nitrogen nutrients and isotopically labeled nutrients and N_2 gas were collected and preserved until later analysis by Bristow.

iii) Microbial interactions and water-column characterization: The team collected samples and data to describe the environment along the water column and characterize physicochemical and biological parameters relevant for metabolic rates and microbial community distribution. These included samples for organic carbon stocks, total cell abundance, pigmented cell abundance, microbial DNA and RNA, and microbial community composition. Samples were also collected for flow imaging analysis, electron microscopy, CARD-FISH, and 16S sequencing to study microalgal community composition and to look for signs of microbial interactions, including nanotubes between picocyanobacteria.

7) HyperPro team

Main aim: Profile the optical properties of the ocean.

Bror Jönsson led the deployment of a Satlantic HyperPro, a profiling free-falling instrument that measures apparent optical properties of the ocean, particularly upwelling and downwelling irradiance. Data from the HyperPro are hyperspectrally resolved and measure light irradiance at 134 wavelengths from 350 to 700 nm.

The HyperPro was deployed using a protocol adapted from the HOT program, aiming to measure three profiles down to 60 m depth in rapid order. The actual length of the profiles varied due to currents and ship positioning. Deployments were performed at different times of day to reflect diurnal variability in the quality and quantity of the measured light field. The instrument was also deployed under different weather conditions, from clear sky to full cloud coverage. While sea state and wind conditions varied among deployments, conditions remained mild, typical of the region. In total, 43 deployments were conducted, of which 38 were successful, capturing representative variability in light conditions for the region during the cruise.

The raw output from the instrument was processed using Satlantic's, now Seabird's, ProSoft version 7.7 to level 2, converting engineering units to scientific units but not mapping them to depth. The data were further processed by converting time to depth by matching observations from the two radiometers with depth information from the internal depth sensor. Finally, the

data were interpolated to even depth levels at 1 m intervals, and repeated profiles were averaged for each deployment when available.

2.1.2 Innovative Technologies

Mini Trace Analyzer In Situ Logger (mTAIL)

During the cruise, the Mini Trace Analyzer In Situ Logger (mTAIL) was deployed for the first time as a state-of-the-art, three-channel oxygen sensing platform for ultra-sensitive dissolved oxygen measurements in marine environments. By supporting multiple sensor types, the system achieves an exceptionally wide dynamic measurement range, spanning from approximately 1000 μM down to 0.1 nM, enabling high-resolution characterization across both oxygen-rich and near-anoxic conditions. The oxygen sensors exhibit fast response times (<5 seconds), making mTAIL particularly well suited for high-resolution vertical profiling when deployed alongside conventional CTD systems. In addition to oxygen sensing, the instrument incorporates integrated pressure and temperature sensors, as well as three auxiliary analog input channels. All sensor data are synchronously sampled and stored in onboard memory at a default rate of 0.5 Hz, which can be user-configured to lower sampling frequencies for extended deployments.

Chamber Oxygen Collector Kit Trace Analyzer In Situ Logger (CockTail)

These unique autonomous in situ incubators enable bulk and single cell rate measurements under in situ pressure, light, temperature, and O_2 conditions. All critical components are constructed from glass and titanium to avoid O_2 contamination. When deployed at depth, the incubator autonomously flushes and fills glass incubation chambers while injecting isotope-labelled substrate. Subsamples are withdrawn and preserved at pre-set intervals, and O_2 is monitored inside and outside the chambers using high-sensitivity sensors. Continuous O_2 monitoring inside the incubation chambers demonstrates our ability to incubate water without detectable O_2 contamination. Two incubators were deployed side by side, initially deployed on a drifting mooring, and then to enable quick turnaround times between incubations was deployed directly off the A-frame. Ten in situ deployments were carried out in total during FKt240412, spanning oxygen gradients of below detection to approx. 2 μM and 85 to 300m water depth. For each deployment, parallel lab incubations were carried out at the same depth (sampled from Niskin bottles) to measure process rates following standard procedures to identify potential biases incurred by conventional sampling.

Pumping Profiling System (PPS)

The PPS enables high-resolution profiling of nutrients, and seawater sampling with minimal O_2 contamination to approximately 300 m depth, complementing CTD-rosette sampling. The system includes a real-time CTD unit with O_2 sensor, PAR (Photosynthetically Active Radiation) sensor, a transmissometer, and an in situ pump deployed from a dedicated winch. A standard 20' laboratory van (4.5–5 tons; UNOLS-approved) houses the CTD deck unit and nutrient autoanalyzer. High-resolution profiles were collected during slow down-casts, while larger

volumes for incubation experiments and omics were sampled at fixed depths during up-casts. Each deployment typically takes 3–4 hours.

2.2 Post-expedition Activities and Accomplishments

2.2.1 Overview

1) In situ team

Our mechanistic and predictive understanding of N loss in today's O₂-depleted waters remains limited. In the traditional view, anaerobic pathways that convey N loss are delineated from aerobic pathways of ammonia and nitrite oxidation that recycle and retain bioavailable N by the absence or presence of O₂. This paradigm of an O₂-controlled switch between loss and recycling is not compatible with emerging evidence of active aerobic metabolisms, including nitrite oxidation, under apparently anoxic conditions. To date, biases from sampling-induced artifacts resulting from changing temperature, pressure, light and most notably O₂ that could sustain aerobic and inhibit anaerobic metabolism, remain undetermined. To address this, we have developed a multi-chamber system for in situ O₂-contamination-free incubations (CockTail). Preliminary results from the OMZ off northern Chile, have revealed striking differences between in situ and traditional shipboard rates, with denitrification rates up to two orders of magnitude higher in situ, implying that only through incubations at environmentally relevant O₂ concentrations can we move towards a mechanistic understanding of N turnover in expanding low O₂ waters. The data workup is ongoing and will be further supplemented in the coming months with in situ single cell growth rates for key N-cycling microbes.

While these in situ incubations represent a major methodological advance - providing an essential benchmark for quantifying sampling biases and capturing N cycling under environmentally relevant O₂ conditions - they are most powerful when integrated with an extensive laboratory-based experimental program. Practical limitations in deployment complexity, depth coverage, and tracer combinations mean that broader laboratory experiments remain necessary to comprehensively resolve the full suite of nitrogen transformation processes across spatial and environmental gradients. High resolution depth profiles were undertaken at both stations, alongside targeted kinetic experiments at selected depths to investigate how varying O₂ and nitrite concentrations influence N transformation pathways. Sample processing and analysis are currently ongoing, with initial results revealing strong gradients in N₂O production and consumption, as well as in N loss and nitrification.

During the cruise, our state-of-the-art high-sensitivity optical O₂ sensor mTAIL was successfully deployed on both the CTD rosette and PPS, generating high-resolution oxygen profiles throughout the study region. These measurements revealed the sporadic presence of nanomolar O₂ pockets in waters traditionally considered persistently anoxic or below conventional detection limits. Particularly notable were data collected during the CTD tow-yo, which produced 30 depth profiles across an 80 km offshore transect. In collaboration with Bastien Queste (University of Gothenburg, Sweden), these observations revealed previously unresolved ventilation processes, identifying a nanomolar O₂ intrusion associated with a subducting filament along the edge of an eddy. This feature was distinguishable through its salinity signature but remained largely

undetectable using standard oxygen sensors. These findings highlight that the rates at which O₂ is supplied and consumed, and thus the extent to which aerobic metabolisms are supported, remain unknown due to limited spatial and temporal coverage of nanomolar O₂ measurements.

2) Microbiaki Lab

Post-expedition analyses by the Microbiaki Lab are focused on linking microbial identity, genomic potential, and transcriptional activity to oxygen gradients and measured biogeochemical rates.

Initial analysis of key nitrogen-cycle genes suggests that many of the abundant microbial families have nitrate reduction potential. In contrast, nitrogen removal capacity appears restricted to only a few lineages, with only three complete denitrifiers identified so far. Several families within Marinisomatota and Bacteroidota have the potential for dissimilatory nitrate reduction to ammonium (DNRA), suggesting that recycling of bioavailable nitrogen compounds may be an important feature of this system. These results are consistent with one of the central questions of the expedition: how nitrogen loss and nitrogen recycling are balanced in oxygen-depleted waters.

The Microbiaki Lab is also using these datasets to investigate nitrite-oxidizing bacteria and other chemolithoautotrophic lineages. Initial results highlight a “nitrifier conundrum”: in most water samples, nitrite-oxidizing bacteria are generally an order of magnitude less abundant than ammonia-oxidizing archaea, raising the question of whether the SAG dataset may be biased by Redox Sensor Green sorting. However, metagenomic mapping suggests that Nitrospinota are more abundant than genome counts alone indicate, particularly when comparing genome recovery with metagenome-based relative abundance.

Phylogenetic and genome-resolved analyses of Nitrospinota suggest the presence of OMZ-associated and potentially endemic lineages, including genera such as UBA7883, CAJXCL01, and CAJWLY01, as well as an endemic clade within Nitromaritima. These lineages appear to occupy distinct ecological niches and differ in genomic and cellular traits such as GC content, cell size, genome size, and growth rates. Growth-rate estimates suggest that Nitrospinota include some of the slowest-growing lineages in the broader marine SAG collection.

Ongoing work includes comparative genomic analyses of Nitrospinota SAGs to identify OMZ-specific features, phylogenetic analyses of other key lineages to investigate endemism, and transcriptomic mapping of key genes involved in nitrogen cycling, sulfur cycling, inorganic carbon fixation, and respiration. A major next step is to decipher sulfur cycling pathways and integrate transcript abundance with rate measurements from the In-Situ, AOA, and MEB teams. Planned manuscripts include a global overview of marine Nitrospinota distribution and genomic potential, and a comparative analysis of chemolithoautotrophic lineages across three low-oxygen systems: the ETSP, ETNP, and Bay of Bengal.

3) AOA team

Pure culture laboratory experiments show that ammonia-oxidizing archaea (AOA), one of the most abundant groups of microbes in the ocean, can produce their own oxygen when exposed to anoxia. This dark oxygen production pathway could sustain obligate aerobes in OMZs when

oxygen is absent and at the same time act as a sink for bioavailable nitrogen competing with other microbial N loss pathways. As no role for AOA in anoxic waters was previously expected, they have rarely been specifically targeted in the anoxic depths of oxygen minimum zones (OMZs), and thus their distribution and activity remain poorly constrained. During the cruise we obtained high resolution profiles for microbial cell counts. CARD-FISH counts revealed that AOA are present at similar high abundances across the full depth profiles including in the anoxic core of the OMZ. Counts are being finalized and the analysis is being extended to other microbial key players. To determine if the AOA cells present in anoxic depths of the OMZ are indeed active we developed click chemistry incubations to test for the activity and growth at the single cell level. Our approach covers amino acid and RNA/DNA nucleoside incorporation to target different facets of cellular activity. We could show that the majority of AOA cells in anoxic depths (~70%) are actively synthesizing RNA demonstrating that most AOA cells are indeed metabolically active. Taken together, our results indicate that AOA are abundant and active in the core of the ETSP and provide a basis for reassessing their potential contribution to biogeochemical cycling within OMZ cores.

Samples collected for stable isotope-proteomics during on board incubations are being analyzed. Using this technique, we can detect the enzymes that different microbial populations are actively synthesizing within a complex environmental community e.g. when exposed to anoxia. This will allow us to identify enzymes with key functions in nitrogen and oxygen cycling. The analyses are ongoing.

4) **Viral team**

In collaboration with Pachiadaki, samples collected aboard R/V *Falkor (too)* during the expedition are enabling expansion of our understanding of the role of viruses within OMZs and discovery of new RNA viruses from this previously unexplored environment. Since the cruise, the Viral team has leveraged samples collected during the expedition and was awarded NSF funding to support the discovery and characterization of novel RNA viruses within oxygen minimum zones.

Post-expedition work has included flow cytometry counts, viral metagenomic analyses, and searches for viral sequences in DNA and RNA datasets generated from FKt240412 samples. Flow cytometry counts have been completed for 39 samples from depth profiles at each station, and these data have been deposited on Zenodo. Initial results show that the ratio of viruses to bacteria is dynamic at low oxygen, suggesting possible changes in infection strategy in response to chemical gradients within the OMZ.

The team has also produced viral metagenomic data from collected samples. Viral particles concentrated at sea were used for DNA extraction and sequencing in collaboration with Maria Pachiadaki and Frank Stewart. These data are being used to examine viral diversity, identify virus-host connections, and investigate the role of viruses in OMZ microbial ecology and nutrient cycling.

New discoveries from the viral datasets include the identification of at least 30 new phages that appear to infect Nitrospina, an important nitrite-oxidizing lineage in oxygen-depleted waters. The team has also identified more than 50 RNA-dependent RNA polymerase genes belonging to novel RNA viruses. These findings suggest that OMZs may harbor previously unknown viral

diversity, including RNA viruses, and that viruses may influence key microbial groups involved in nitrogen cycling.

5) Phytoplankton team

Following the expedition, the Phytoplankton team has continued analyzing complementary datasets to understand how low-oxygen conditions influence phytoplankton physiology and activity across the oxycline. Our main goal is to determine whether oxygen availability, or the broader physicochemical conditions associated with low-oxygen waters, helps explain the decline of most phytoplankton groups at the base of the oxycline (chlorophyll minimum) and the ecological success of OMZ/AMZ-adapted *Prochlorococcus* lineages.

Post-expedition activities have included the analysis of incubation experiments, high-resolution vertical profiles, metatranscriptomic samples, photosynthesis–irradiance curves, and carbon fixation measurements. In the incubation experiments, cultured phytoplankton from the oxic layer of the Eastern South Pacific were exposed to natural waters from the oxic layer and from the base of the oxycline, under light and temperature conditions representative of the oxycline. Preliminary results suggest taxon-specific responses: the coccolithophore *Gephyrocapsa huxleyi* showed signs of inhibition, whereas the diatom *Thalassiosira* sp. appeared more resistant. These findings support the idea that low-oxygen waters, or their associated chemical conditions, may selectively affect different phytoplankton groups.

High-resolution profiles showed that, although no clear secondary chlorophyll maximum was observed during the cruise, fluorescence declined in parallel with oxygen, and transparency maxima occurred below the oxycline. This pattern suggests a strong reduction in phytoplankton biomass near the base of the oxycline, despite the presence of enough light and nutrients to potentially support photosynthesis. Flow cytometry observations also showed that most phytoplankton groups decreased with declining oxygen, although some group-specific patterns were detected, including a small diatom peak at Station 1 and a slower decline of ciliates relative to phytoplankton.

Metatranscriptomic analyses are underway to compare size-fractionated microbial and phytoplankton gene expression between the chlorophyll maximum and chlorophyll minimum layers. Initial bioinformatic processing has been completed, including quality filtering, rRNA removal, exclusion of potential human contamination, and taxonomic classification using Kraken2/Bracken. Next steps include contig assembly, gene prediction, and taxonomic and functional annotation, with targeted analyses of groups such as diatoms and Mamiellales.

Additional analyses include intracellular nitric oxide measurements, photosynthesis–irradiance curves, and carbon fixation rates. Nitric oxide results were not consistent across experiments and remain an open question. Natural abundance samples for carbon fixation have been analyzed, while enriched samples for rate measurements are currently being processed by mass spectrometry. Overall, the expedition has generated two student theses and several planned publications focused on phytoplankton responses to hypoxia, metatranscriptomic contrasts across the oxycline, and nitric oxide signals in plankton communities.

This research addresses a major knowledge gap in understanding how ocean deoxygenation may affect phytoplankton, which sustain marine food webs and play a central role in carbon cycling and climate regulation. By combining experiments, high-resolution profiles, flow cytometry, metatranscriptomics, photosynthesis–irradiance curves, and carbon fixation measurements, the project provides an integrated view of how phytoplankton respond to natural low-oxygen waters in the Eastern South Pacific.

Preliminary results suggest that low-oxygen waters, or their associated physicochemical conditions, may affect phytoplankton groups differently, potentially reshaping community composition and influencing carbon fixation, food-web structure, and biogeochemical cycling. These outcomes are relevant for policymakers because oxygen minimum zones are expected to expand under climate change, making it essential to improve predictions of ecosystem vulnerability, fisheries productivity, and coastal biogeochemical change.

For local communities, this work helps anticipate how changes at the base of the food web may affect marine resources and food security. The project also contributes to capacity building by supporting graduate and undergraduate theses and training students in oceanographic sampling, phytoplankton physiology, and microbial ecology.

6) MEB Lab

Samples collected for study the small fraction of the phytoplankton community were analyzed by Imaging Flow Cytometry in the laboratory of the Ecology section at the University of Cadiz (Spain). The analyses reveal the presence of nanotubes connecting the tiny cells of the picoplankton; although they are present in a relatively low percentage (<2.5%) of the cells, this is the first time their presence in these oceanic communities has been demonstrated. In nutrient-poor environments such as the oligotrophic ocean, these nanotubes facilitate cooperation and the exchange of resources, which could be a critical factor in the ecological success of picocyanobacteria, the most abundant photosynthetic organisms on Earth.

The microbial community plays a significant role in the formation and maintenance of the hypoxic and anoxic conditions characteristics of the OMZs. The response of the microbial community to decreasing oxygen levels was investigated during on board incubations. The high complexity involved in handling near-anoxic samples in an oxygen-rich atmosphere poses a significant methodological challenge. During the incubations conducted, the intrusion of oxygen into various incubation vessels has made it difficult to obtain clear data describing the metabolism of the microbial community across an oxygen gradient.

2.2.2 New Discoveries

Most of the analyses are still ongoing; some of the initial new discoveries include:

- Since the cruise, we have been querying DNA and RNA sequence data generated from samples collected, searching for viral sequences. We have identified at least 30 new phages that appear to be infecting Nitrospina, and over 50 RNA-dependent RNA Polymerase genes belonging to novel RNA viruses.
- Preliminary results suggest taxon-specific response to low oxygen: the coccolithophore *Gephyrocapsa huxleyi* showed signs of growth rate inhibition, whereas the diatom

Thalassiosira cf. tenere appeared less affected. These findings support the idea that low-oxygen waters, or their associated chemical conditions, may selectively affect different phytoplankton groups.

- The presence of nanotubes among picoplankton cells has been demonstrated in the phytoplankton community of the South Pacific.

2.2.3 Software Utilized

- Oxygen measurements: PreSens Measurement Studio 2 (PreSens GmbH); PyroWorkBench & Oxygen logger (Pyroscience GmbH)
- Analysis of microscopic images: Fiji (ImageJ) - Schindelin, J., Arganda-Carreras, I., Frise, E., Kaynig, V., Longair, M., Pietzsch, T., ... Cardona, A. (2012). Fiji: an open-source platform for biological-image analysis. *Nature Methods*, 9(7), 676–682. doi:10.1038/nmeth.2019
- CTD-PPS deployment: SeaSave and SBE Data Processing
- Nutrient Analyzer SEAL QuAAtro39, software: AACE version 7.11
- Influx Flow Cytometer software: FlowJo
- FIRE Fluorometer software: FIREview, FIREPro (v1.20)
- Imaging Flow Cytometry: IDEAS® Software

2.3 Data

Datasets acquired during this expedition and those derived from the analysis of collected data and samples as of this report's publication date are displayed below.

Data Type	Repository	Status
Vessel underway data	Rolling Deck to Repository	Completed
ADCP	University of Hawaii Data Acquisition System	Completed
Processed Multibeam from <i>Falkor (too)</i>	Marine Geoscience Data System (MGDS)	Completed
Nitrogen samples	Zenodo	Currently uploaded
Metaproteomics		
Radiance data collected from the HyperPro instrument	Zenodo	Completed
Processed CTD data	Marine Geoscience Data System (MGDS)	Completed
N cycling rates	Zenodo	In-progress
Relative abundance data of ammonia oxidizers and single cell activity	Zenodo	In-progress
Phytoplankton incubation experiments	Zenodo	In-progress
Viromes	GenBank/NCBI	In-progress
Oxygen consumption / aerobic respiration	Zenodo	In-progress
Viruses, prokaryotes and protists count	Zenodo	Completed
Molecular data	GenBank/NCBI	In-progress

3 Appendix

3.1 Science Party Information

Scientist	Institution
Alisa Wurst	University of Gothenburg
Annabelle Adams-Beyea	Montana State University
Beate Kraft	University of Southern Denmark
Bror Jonsson	University of New Hampshire

Scientist	Institution
Christopher Basque	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution
Elisa Angulo-Canovas	University of Cádiz
Elisa Hernandez Magana	University of Southern Denmark
Emilio Garcia Robledo	University of Cádiz
Emilio Espinoza Salas	Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile
Fabian Cortes Lillo	Universidad de Concepción
Gadiel Alarcon Coronado	Universidad de Concepción
Gerardo Garcia Ruiz	Universidad de Concepción
Julia Huggins	University of Cádiz
Julia Brown	Bigelow Laboratory for Ocean Sciences
Laura Bristow	University of Gothenburg
Lizt Osorio Pando	Ensenada Center for Scientific Research and Higher Education (CICESE)
Maria Pachiadaki	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution
Monsterrat Aldunate Chinchon	Universidad de Concepción
Morten Larsen	University of Southern Denmark
Natalia Cistemas Pena	Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service (SHOA)
Oswaldo Ulloa Quijada	Universidad de Concepción
Peter Von Dassow	Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile
Sibille Amestica Guzman	Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile
Sina Schorn	University of Gothenburg
Taylor Heyl	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution
Tim D'Angelo	Bigelow Laboratory for Ocean Sciences

Table 2. List of scientists and students aboard *Falkor (too)*.

3.2 Conferences/Presentations/Posters

Laura A. Bristow, Bo Thamdrup, and Morten Larsen (2025). Recycling versus loss: aerobes, anaerobes and everything in-between. Oral presentation, Baltic Sea Nitrogen Cycling Network Workshop, Uppsala, Sweden.

Laura A. Bristow, Virginia P. Edgcomb, Katharina Kitziinger, Maria G. Pachiadaki, Sina Schorn, Bo Thamdrup, Alisa R. I. Wüst, Emily J. Zakem, and Morten Larsen (2025). Denitrification as the dominant nitrogen loss pathway in oxygen-depleted waters: an in situ approach. Oral presentation, ICoN9 – Ninth International Conference on Nitrification and Related Processes, Bremen, Germany.

Laura A. Bristow (2025). Recycling versus loss in the marine nitrogen cycle: a new perspective. Keynote talk, European Nitrogen Cycling Meeting, Vienna, Austria.

Laura A. Bristow, Annie Bourbonnais, Virginia P. Edgcomb, Claire E. Elbon, Katharina Kitziinger, Maria G. Pachiadaki, Sina Schorn, Bo Thamdrup, Alisa R. I. Wüst, Emily J. Zakem, and Morten

Larsen (2026). Recycling versus loss in the marine nitrogen cycle: an in situ perspective. Oral presentation, Ocean Sciences Meeting, Glasgow, UK.

Maria Pachiadaki, R. Hamilton, T. Chang, R. Stepanauskas, and the GORG consortium (2025). Dark ocean chemolithoautotrophy: Novel insights from ten thousand single-cell genomes. Aquatic Sciences Meeting, Charlotte, North Carolina, USA.

Maria Pachiadaki and the GORG consortium (2024). Dark ocean chemolithoautotrophy: Novel insights from ten thousand single-cell genomes. ISME19, Cape Town, South Africa.

Julia M. Brown (2025). Integrated 'omics uncovers phage-host dynamics in the ETNP oxygen minimum zone. Oral presentation, Association for the Sciences of Limnology and Oceanography (ASLO) Aquatic Sciences Meeting, Charlotte, North Carolina, USA.

Julia M. Brown (2025). Disentangling virus-microbe interactions to uncover dynamic and novel roles of viruses in marine ecosystems. Invited seminar, Colby College Biology Department.

Julia M. Brown (2024). Insights into marine viral ecology from individual connections. Invited seminar, Southern Maine Community College Department of Marine Science.

Beate Kraft (2024). Ecophysiology of ammonia-oxidizing archaea under oxygen depletion. Invited talk, EMBO Conference 'Molecular Biology of Archaea,' Paris, France.

Beate Kraft (2024). Coping with oxygen depletion: A pathway out for nitrifiers. Invited talk, online seminar series of the Research Action Network for Reducing Reactive Nitrogen Losses from Agricultural Ecosystems.

Beate Kraft (2024). Microbial oxygen production in the dark. Roundtable host, International Society for Microbial Ecology (ISME) Meeting, Cape Town, South Africa.

Montserrat Aldunate (2026). Ocean deoxygenation in the Eastern South Pacific. Oral presentation, scientific session 'The Science of Global-ONCE and Some Examples of Marine Research at UdeC,' Universidad de Concepción.

Peter von Dassow (2025). Phytoplankton in oxygen minimum zones and anoxic marine zones: Why is the oxycline a barrier to phytoplankton? Oral presentation, XLIV Congress of Marine Sciences, Viña del Mar, Chile.

Osvaldo Ulloa (2025). When the oceans suffocate, the microbes will play. Keynote presentation, XLIV Congress of Marine Sciences, Viña del Mar, Chile.

Emilio Espinoza-Salas (2025). Inhibición de fitoplancton eucarionte en las zonas mínimas de oxígeno [Inhibition of eukaryotic phytoplankton in oxygen minimum zones]. Presentation, XLIV Congress of Marine Sciences, Viña del Mar, Chile.

Montserrat Aldunate (2025). Microscopic organisms in hypoxia: ecophysiological rates and their role in the carbon cycle. Trevor Platt Science Foundation Webinar.

Peter von Dassow (2025). El mar frente a Chile y la belleza de fitoplancton: ¿Cómo el plancton vive y adapta en el océano en cambio? [The sea off Chile and the beauty of phytoplankton: How

does plankton live and adapt in a changing ocean?]. Invited seminar, Núcleo Milenio para el Estudio de la Desoxigenación del Océano (DEOXS), Pontificia Universidad Católica de Valparaíso, Curauma, Chile.

Peter von Dassow (2025). Microscopic organisms under hypoxia: ecophysiological rates and their role in the carbon cycle. Invited seminar, Núcleo Milenio para el Estudio de la Desoxigenación del Océano (DEOXS), Pontificia Universidad Católica de Valparaíso, Curauma, Chile.

Oswaldo Ulloa (2024). The globally significant cyanobacterium *Prochlorococcus* may have originated in a low-oxygen ocean. Keynote presentation, ISME19, Cape Town, South Africa.

Fabián Cortés (2024). Response of the surface phytoplankton community to hypoxia in the oxygen minimum zone off the coast of continental Chile. Oral presentation, XLIII Congress of Marine Sciences, Chile.

Montserrat Aldunate (2024). Microscopic organisms under hypoxia: their role in the carbon cycle. Seminar, Ocean Deoxygenation: A Perspective from Northern Chile, University of Antofagasta, Chile.

3.3 Student Projects, Thesis, and Dissertations

Alisa R. I. Wüst (PhD ongoing, 2024–2028). Nitrous oxide dynamics in oxygen-depleted waters. University of Gothenburg, Sweden.

Lena S. Wischnat (MSc, 2025–2026). Comparison of nitrogen loss pathways and their environmental drivers in the Bay of Bengal and Eastern South Pacific oxygen minimum zones. University of Gothenburg, Sweden.

Oskar Wangdell (MSc, 2025–2026). Environmental controls and distribution of nitrification in oxygen-depleted marine waters. University of Gothenburg, Sweden.

Clara Hiel (Master's internship, 2025). Characterising ecological niches of methane-oxidising and nitrite-oxidising bacteria in anoxic waters. University of Gothenburg, Sweden.

Annabelle Adams-Beyea (PhD ongoing, 2025–present). Pelagibacterales and their associated viruses. Montana State University. Uses FKt240412 samples as part of her thesis research.

Josephine Pikowski (undergraduate independent research project, Bigelow Laboratory Sea Change Semester, 2025). Microbial and viral particle counts from the ETSP OMZ water column.

Elisa Angulo-Cánovas (PhD thesis, to be defended in late 2026). Interactions between marine cyanobacteria via extracellular vesicles and nanotubes. Universidad de Córdoba, Spain.

Emilio Espinoza (undergraduate thesis in Biochemistry, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile). Inhibition of eukaryotic phytoplankton in oxygen minimum zones; nitric oxide experiments and responses of eukaryotic phytoplankton to low-oxygen/oxycline waters.

Fabián Cortés (Master's thesis in Oceanography, Universidad de Concepción). Response of the surface phytoplankton community to hypoxia; response of cultured phytoplankton strains exposed to LowOx treatments and natural oxycline waters.

3.4 Cruise Records

Six videos were produced for the expedition. The videos have garnered 6,000 views since being posted to the Schmidt Ocean Institute YouTube Channel.

- [Exploring an Invisible World in the Ocean](#)
- [Studying a Globally Important Environment](#)
- [A Hidden Microbial World](#)
- [Adventure at the Frontier of Science \(ft. Dr. Osvaldo Ulloa\)](#)
- [Aventura en la frontera de la ciencia \(ft. Dr. Osvaldo Ulloa\)](#)
- [Motherhood, Ocean Science, and an Interconnected World \(ft. Montserrat Aldunate\)](#)

3.5 Media

- Clunes, A., von Dassow, P., and Ulloa, O. (18 May 2024). Hacer visible lo invisible: arte y ciencia en el mar [Making the invisible visible: art and science at sea]. El Mostrador.
- Las Últimas Noticias interview (1 June 2024). Expedición fue a la zona del Océano Pacífico donde no hay oxígeno [Expedition traveled to the region of the Pacific Ocean where there is no oxygen].

3.6 Community Outreach

- 8 Ship-to-shore connections occurred during the expedition, engaging a total of 382 people in Chile and the United States. A Schmidt Ocean Institute-hosted Open House reached 1500 people.
- Inviernos con Ciencia [Winters with Science], organized by the Ministry of Cultures, Arts and Heritage at the Santiago Library. Participated as the PhytoDELICA lab (Phytoplankton Diversity, Ecology and Life Cycle Adaptations), 24 July 2024 and 31 July 2025.
- A press release went out on 21 May 2025, resulting in 12 written publications in Chile and the U.S. Notable coverage included ECO Magazine and Marine Technology News.
- Schmidt Ocean Institute Ship-to-Shore seminars from *Falkor (too)* to Trewhela's School (19 April 2024) and Fundación Desierto Azul (11 May 2024).
- Julia Brown gave a "5-minute Genius" presentation for the Maine Science Festival highlighting this work.
- Julia Brown participated in four Skype a Scientist interviews with grade-school classrooms after the cruise and shared her experience at sea working with the FKt240412 science team.